

Project Partners: 1. LEITAT 2. IOM 3. CEA 4. TECNALIA 5. UKCEH 6. CNRS 7. RIVM 8. GAIKER 9. FIOH 10. ISTECH 11. THINKWORKS 12. ALLIOS 13. LATI 14. NOURYON 15. SYMLOG 16. DUKE UNIVERSITY	 H2020-NMBP-15-2020 Simple, robust and cost-effective approaches to guide industry in the development of safer nanomaterials and nano-enabled products Start date of the project: 01/03/2020 Duration 48 months <h2 style="text-align: center;">Communication toolbox including a large set of basic communication materials</h2>
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WP	8	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and RRI		
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Lead beneficiary	Leitat
Contributing beneficiaries	All

¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Email	Comments ³
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³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

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1. Introduction

This deliverable aims to present the communication materials developed for the SAbYNA project in order to assure a high-quality communication during its execution. Several materials were created in digital and printed format. This includes a logo, a website, a leaflet, a roll-up and a Twitter account. Its use by all the partners will greatly increase the project's visibility. On top of that, several pieces of content have been created and disseminated widely. In addition, this deliverable presents in greater detail the communication and dissemination plan for the SAbYNA project for the upcoming 4 years by setting the main lines with accompanying objectives, channels and activities.

2. Objective

The communication materials of SAbYNA aim to provide the basic support to all partners for their dissemination and communication activities during the entire project duration. They sum up the basic information about the project as well as its developments, milestones and results. This task runs during the whole project duration in order to achieve as early as possible grounding toward successful communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results. The activities aim at communicating and disseminating information and results of the project within the partners and outside the consortium.

For the communication (defined as the promotion of the project and its results in a non-specialised language), the messages will concentrate on the following themes: safe-by-design, nanomaterials, nano-enabled products, 3D printing, paints.

The materials produced will be updated during the project lifetime and aim to demonstrate how SAbYNA advances are important contributions to the research and industry. These materials will be used during every type of event, face-to-face meeting, scientific conferences, workshops, and networks such as ETPs. The SAbYNA consortium will also establish linkages and collaborations with relevant other projects and initiatives to amplify the impact of the project. An important event will be the design and organisation of the final SAbYNA project conference. For these events, good communication materials are essential.

All communication and dissemination materials produced have the EU emblem, the acknowledgment of funding and the disclaimer. The communication manager will put efforts to assure that this is the case for all materials produced during the project execution.

3. Content

3.1 Logo

The brand: The logo has been created according to the most relevant features of the SAbYNA project and aims to represent it conceptually. Based on the acronym of the project and respecting the upper-case and lower-case letters of SAbYNA, the logo has a unique font, specific colours, and an icon. The main colour of the logo is blue, as it refers to the technological and safety character on which the project is based. The shield, made of particles, being the icon and integrated with the letters, symbolizes the safety and the nanomaterials. Then, aesthetic effects have been added by overlapping the shield with the "S" of SAbYNA, the "b" and the "y" have a different colour and are in a different position and have a different style than the rest of the letters. Below the final design of the logo.

Master placement: The logo should be placed primarily on a white background, but in certain cases it can be put on photos or other colours, making sure it is visible enough. The logo is the only representation of the project and the design has been approved by the consortium. It should not be modified nor redesigned without specific authorization, as this could harm the project image.

Use: The measure of the free space that should surround the logo is the height equal to the letter “A” of the logo. This is the mandatory minimum and should be higher whenever possible. The free space should not be used as a guide to place the SAbyNA logo in a material, since the positioning depends on other factors such as the proportion or the size of the material.

Digital landmark: When the logo appears in a digital publication, its minimum width can not be less than 110 pixels. When using only the “S Shield” as an isolated icon, its minimum width should not be smaller than 30 pixels.

Minimum digital size

Printed landmark: When the mark is issued in printed publications, its minimum width may not be less than 30 millimeters. When using the “S” Shield” as an isolated icon, its minimum width should not be less than 10 millimeters.

Greyscale: For black and white publications, a grey tone with 80% black may be used on the entire logo except for the “by” which will be 50% black.

Black or white watermark: This option is of very limited use and the original brand must be used, but in certain cases where the design requires a dark or light support, SAbyNA blue colours can be substituted for white and black. The shading of the “S” disappears so its use should be limited.

Brandmark greyscale

Brandmark Black

Brandmark: White on a dark background, preferably any of the three primary color blues (limited use)

Incorrect usage: The SAbYNA logo should only be used using the approved files and should not be modified.

1. Do not alter the positioning or size of the brandmark elements.

X

2. Do not alter or change the fonts.

X

3. Do not change the brandmark colours.

X

4. Do not change the brandmark angle.

X

5. Do not distort the brandmark.

X

6. Do not apply tint or effects to the brandmark.

X

7. Do not use white brandmark on a light background.

X

8. Do not use master brandmark on a dark background.

X

9. Do not use brandmark on highcontrast images, or dark image.

X

Primary colours: The three primary colours represented below with their different nomenclatures are those that make up the SAbYNA logo.

Primary Colour Palette

"Metallblau"
PANTONE 194 U
c87 m66 y23 k0
R71 G98 B148
#476294

"Blaular"
PANTONE 660 U
c77 m49 y3 k0
R98 G127 B190
#627FBE

Dark blue
PANTONE 2767 C
c94 m90 y52 k26
R37 G48 B76
#25304C

Secondary colours: The secondary colours have been created to design elements in the brand's publications. Different shades of the same colour can be used within its chromatic range. Never substitute primary colours for secondary ones.

Secondary Colour Palette, Limited Use, For PPT Presentations, Charts, Graphs

Smooth gradient
Clearblau 50%
Dark blue 50%

Grey
PANTONE P 175-16 U
c65 m57 y57 k35
R58 G58 B58
#4f4f4f

Turquoise
PANTONE 7473 U
c95 m00 y65 k00
R00 G168 B136
#00A888

Fonts: The main typographic family that should be used is Roboto. It must be used in the titles of the different publications and outstanding texts. The secondary typography is Sen. It should be used for texts that are not titles. To highlight words or phrases, the bold style can be used. We discourage to use the underline option.

Primari Typeface:

Roboto light

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Roboto Medium

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Roboto bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Secondary Typeface:

Sen Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Sen bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

3.2 Website

SAbyNA project benefits from its own website since M3 and presents the project objectives and activities. It is the project's main digital communication channel and is being updated on a regular basis. It is accessible here: <https://www.sabyna.eu/>

It aims to present the project in a visual and attractive way. As the activities of the project are easy to represent in a graphical manner, the consortium will try to benefit from it as much as possible to ensure an excellent communication.

The first page shows the great characteristics of the project's Safe-by-Design concept with visual images that show the main activities of SAbyNA. A button drives the visitor to the next page of the website, which explains in greater detail the objectives of the project. There is a progression of complexity of the information, starting with simple information to more and more complex one in order that each visitor can pick the amount of information he/she is seeking for.

The news section, also displayed on the home page, will be updated regularly with important news related to the project such as meetings. In the future, intermediary results will also be published to inform the stakeholders about the public developments.

It integrates various pages such as the description of work packages, the links to other related projects and organizations, and a detailed description of the partners forming the SAbyNA consortium. The website has a publications page, on which all public publications such as posters, presentation, papers, and other documents or data produced by the SAbyNA project will be made freely available. Last, it integrated a registration form for developing a broad stakeholder database that will be crucial in the development of the project. The website will be maintained for at least 5 years.

The website is mobile friendly, its content has been optimised for search engines and it will be linked with various websites to increase its positioning in search results. It is constantly monitored by an analytical system providing detailed insights about the traffic such as audience, behaviour and acquisition.

Last, it has a small subscription form where visitors can leave their email address and they will receive the main updated about the project by email such as newsletters, main news items, and invitations to test the Guidance Platform. This database will be managed according to the RGPD.

Below a few screenshots of the website:

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the SAbyNA website with the logo on the left and menu items: Home, Project, Work Packages, Links, Partners, Publications, Contact. Below the navigation is a large banner image with a white text box containing the following text:

SAbyNA aims to provide the industry with a user-friendly, customized and integrative guidance platform to support the development of safe-by-design nanomaterials and nano-enabled products. The SAbyNA guidance platform will integrate various available resources such as methods, models, frameworks and tools to reduce complexity and costs. Users will be able to identify the potential risks, be able to establish optimal workflows and find solutions to reduce or mitigate the risks associated to their innovation process.

Below the text box is a button that says "More about the project...".

This section of the website features a newsletter subscription form. It includes the SAbyNA logo, the heading "Subscribe To Our Newsletter", and the text "Join our mailing list to receive the latest news and updates from our team." Below this is a form with an "Email" input field and a blue "SUBSCRIBE!" button.

Below the form is a "Partners" section with a horizontal line. It displays a grid of logos for various partner organizations, including LEITAT, IOM, cca, tecnalia, LATI, Nouryon, CITE, SYMLOG, GAIKER, Finnish Institute of Occupational Health, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Duke, NIST, and allios.

The "Why SAbyNA?" section has a dark blue background with a white molecular structure graphic on the right. The heading "Why SAbyNA?" is in large white font. The text below reads:

Numerous organizations have produced guidance documents with the aim of covering the obvious risk management gap that exists in workers, consumers and environment with nanoparticles. Many types of nanoforms and uses exist and the human and environmental health risk may vary profoundly.

Work packages

3.3 Leaflet

The second communication material of SAbYNA is the leaflet, which is distributed in printed and digital format. In 8 pages, it aims to present visually and graphically the aim, the specific objectives and the main outputs of the project in an attractive manner.

It aims to be used for any face to face meeting, public event, conference or any other occasion by the partners to promote the project and inform stakeholders.

According to the needs of the consortium, more will be printed, or new versions will be published including updated information. Below the first version of the leaflet:

Why SAbYNA?

Numerous organizations have produced guidance documents with the aim of improving risk management of nanomaterials and protecting health of workers, consumers and environment. Many types of nanoforms and uses exist and the human and environmental health risks may vary profoundly.

SAbYNA aims to improve the usability of existing databases, test methods, models, frameworks and tools and integrating them into an interactive and user-friendly web-based guidance.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- 1 Map and establish hierarchies of the most relevant existing resources that can support safe by design of nanotechnology.
- 2 Establish simple, robust and cost-effective human and environmental hazard, exposure, and risk assessment strategies.
- 3 Improve usability of existing tools for risk identification and risk assessment, with a special focus of GUIDEnano.
- 4 Propose safe by design strategies to eliminate or reduce risks at the design stage of Industrial Innovation process.
- 5 Develop the SAbYNA Guidance Platform Integrating selected resources to propose safe by design strategies to maximize safety while maintaining product functionality.
- 6 Implement and validate the applicability of the SAbYNA guidance platform in 3D printing and paints sectors.

3.4 Roll Up

The roll-up is a further communication material that will rather be used in a printed format during events such as fairs and conferences where the project will have a stand. It aims to explain very briefly that SAbYNA is developing a Guidance Platform for the production safer nanomaterials and nano-enabled products with some unique features. It should attract attention and be visually appealing.

As the leaflet and according to the needs, new versions will be created along the development of the project.

The poster features a blue background with a molecular structure pattern at the top. The SAbYNA logo is prominently displayed in the center. Below the logo, a text box explains the project's goal: "SAbYNA aims to improve the usability of existing databases, test methods, models, frameworks and tools and integrate them into an interactive web-based guidance platform". A central diagram shows three interconnected boxes labeled "DATABASES", "DOCUMENTS AND GUIDELINES", and "METHODS, TOOLS AND MODELS", all pointing to a central box that reads "A user-friendly guidance platform for the industry". At the bottom left, contact information is provided: "www.sabyrna.eu", "info@sabyrna.eu", and "@SAbYNA2020". The bottom right section lists "PARTNERS" and the "Coordinator" LEITAT, with logos for various organizations including UK Research and Innovation, IOM, cea, tecnalia, LATI, Nouryon, CNRS, SYMLOG, GAIKER, Finnish Institute of Occupational Health, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Duke, NIST, and allios. A small box at the very bottom contains the European Union flag and a disclaimer: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862419. This publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein."

3.5 Twitter

The project created a Twitter account for two main purposes: the first one, to communicate smaller pieces of news and to amplify the ones published on the website to drive traffic; and the second one, to interact with stakeholders, mainly industries in the field of nanosafety and to raise awareness around SAbYNA. All members of the consortium are encouraged to actively provide content and tweet about their activities to position SAbYNA and especially its Guidance Platform as a reference in the field.

The project account is the following: <https://twitter.com/SAbYNA2020> - @SAbYNA2020

The image shows a screenshot of a Twitter profile for SAbyNA (@SAbyNA2020). On the left is a navigation sidebar with icons for Home, Explore, Notifications, Messages, Bookmarks, Lists, Profile, and More, along with a blue 'Tweet' button. The profile header features the SAbyNA logo, which consists of a molecular structure and the text 'SAbyNA'. Below the logo is the bio: 'Industry Guidance Platform for the development of safe nanomaterials and nano-enabled products'. There is an 'Edit profile' button. The profile information includes the name 'SAbyNA', the handle '@SAbyNA2020', a bio describing it as an #H2020 project, location 'Europe', a website link 'https://t.co/Mhb62w97he', and 'Joined March 2020'. It also shows '36 Following' and '4 Followers'. Below the profile information are tabs for 'Tweets', 'Tweets & replies', 'Media', and 'Likes'. A 'Who to follow' section is visible at the bottom, showing 'Projekt DaNa4.0 and 3 others follow'.

3.6 Templates

Word and Power Point templates (for deliverables, minutes, presentations and posters) have been designed. They are used by the partners to write the deliverables and presentations about the project, and they are a great tool to strengthen the brand recognition.

Figure 1: Presentation template (various options available)

Figure 2: Meeting minutes template

Figure 4: Poster template (various options available)

Figure 3: Deliverable template

3.7 Press release

On the 11th of March, when the kick-off meeting of SAbYNA project was held, a press release was distributed to all project partners for publication. The aim of this press release is to raise awareness around SAbYNA project for the first time.

Below the press release:

Contributing to the safe development of nanomaterials

by SAbYNA Project | Mar 11, 2020 | Uncategorized | 0 comments

Within the framework of a safe and sustainable innovation in the field of nanotechnology, it is necessary to know the potential risks associated with the development and use of nanotechnology-based products. If we add to that the great variety of nanomaterials and how they interact in different environments, it becomes difficult to generate guidelines and protocols for action to prevent the potential associated risks.

Therefore, Leitat coordinates the SAbYNA project that aims to create an online platform that serves as an easy-to-use guide for the industry working with nanomaterials and thus allows them to minimize risks for workers, consumers and environment. The final objective of the project is to organize, simplify and integrate the resources already available in a single platform (SAbYNA Guidance Platform) that allows the industry to incorporate the concepts of safety and sustainability in its innovation processes from the early stages of product design and taking into account all stages of its life cycle.

This project is financed by the European Union in the framework of the Horizon 2020 framework with a budget of almost 6 million euros. It is led by the technology centre Leitat in Barcelona and counts 16 partners from 8 different countries.

The kick-off meeting took place on March 11 and 12.

It has been published on the following websites:

- <https://www.sabyna.eu/contributing-to-the-safe-development-of-nanomaterials/>
- <https://projects.leitat.org/leitat-contributes-to-the-safe-development-of-nanomaterials/>
- <https://mundoplast.com/gaiker-guia-seguridad-nanomateriales/>
- <https://www.interempresas.net/Proteccion-laboral/Articulos/303379-Guia-interactiva-para-implementar-estrategias-diseno-seguro-sector-nanotecnologia.html>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/418375-a-new-guidance-platform-contributing-to-the-safe-development-of-nanomaterials>

3.8 Infographics

Different infographics about the SAbyNA project, its objectives and its main features have been designed and used in the project communication materials such as the leaflet, the roll-up, the website and the social media. They are a great help to explain the project in an easy and quickly way. For the moment, three have been produced and put into the leaflet and roll up. More will be produced during the project execution, especially one explaining the role of each partner and the main tasks of the project.

Below the current ones:

3.9 Document Repository

A dedicated private document repository has been setup since the very beginning of the project. Each member of the consortium has a unique access and can upload and download documents securely with the rest of the consortium. This application is hosted on Leitat's own server and is based on Nextcloud, an open source cloud solution. It will be available for the entire project duration and beyond if necessary.

It can be accessed through the following link: <https://docs.leitat.org>

4. Communication and Dissemination Plan

Different activities are planned the four upcoming years to develop the communication and dissemination of the project. On the one hand side, the SAbyNA project will carry out dissemination activities, that will target the scientific community and concentrate on the public disclosure of results in a scientific or specialist language prioritizing accuracy and the delivery of information to those who will use it. On the other hand side, communication activities will be carried out and will involve the public promotion of the project and its results in clear language to a non-specialist audience, with the objective of increasing public awareness.

4.1 Dissemination activities

4.1.1 Publications

The SAbyNA consortium aims to publish scientific articles in high impact factor journals including: Nanotoxicology, Nanoimpact, Small, Sustainability; Journal of Hazardous Materials, Nanomaterials, Journal of Aerosol Science, Toxicology Research, ES Nano, Env. Sci. Technol; Public Understanding of Science, Journal of Risk Research, and Safety Science. The consortium will ensure that the publications will be available in open access and contribute to open science and open innovation.

4.1.2 Conferences

The consortium partner will make oral and poster presentations at several high level European and international conferences, Specific emphasis on U.S based conference will be given to foster the EU-US collaboration. Conferences include Nanocon, NanoSafe, Euro PM, NanoTox, European Environmental Mutagenesis & Genomics Society meeting, Eurotox, ICEENN, ACS, The European Masterbatchers & Compounders and industrial sector fairs, and International Conference of Environmental Psychology amongst others. Due to the current travel and events restrictions, these dissemination activities might be limited for the beginning of the project but will be compensated once normality is back.

4.1.3 Workshops

Three workshops will be organized during the project duration:

1. Stakeholder Workshop & Presentation of SAbyNA Guidance Platform: Workshop to coincide with the second release of SAbyNA Guidance to gather feedback from users. This event aims to facilitate the collection of feedback from different stakeholders that will help in the construction of the SAbyNA Guidance Platform which it will cover the needs of the future users. The goal is to share the projects outcome and potential impacts and engage all actors in one place to have a productive dialogue about the future of safety and SbD of NF and NEP. It will take place in month 32 meaning around September 2022.
2. Open Technical Workshop to present and disseminate the project outcomes after three years. Its will take place as a side event of a larger conference in month 36, meaning around March 2023.
3. Final conference being a larger event organized with other Nanosafety Cluster projects and other projects funded under the same topic to bring together recognized scientist and experts within the field. The conference will include keynote speakers from the industry, regulatory bodies and the scientific community along with the consortium participation. Similar to the conference organized in Malaga in February 2017. This event should take place in month 48 of the project, meaning in February 2024.

4.1.4 Webinars

Organization of the Stakeholders webinars (in accordance with the stakeholder workshop) together with WP6 to facilitate the collection of feedback from different stakeholders. This will help the consortium in the construction of the SAbyNA Guidance Platform covering the needs of the future users. In addition, it will extend its stakeholder network. One webinar will coincide with the release of the first version of SAbyNA Guidance as part of WP6 in month 22, being January 2022. Another webinar will be organized later during the project according to the development of the Platform with the similar aim.

4.1.5 Summer School

A Summer School for PhD, Post-Doc students and young scientists will be organised around the theme of Safe by Design of nanomaterials and nano enabled products. It will involve mainly the research and academic partners such as research centres and universities. It will allow to communicate the knowledge generated in the project and include a training on the use of the SAbyNA Guidance Platform. It should be organized in month 36, meaning around March 2023.

4.1.6 Activities in platforms

A number of partners are already members of several networks, platforms and associations including Nanosafety Cluster, NIA, European Observatory on Nanomaterials (EUON), European Research in Occupational Safety and Health (PEROSH), Nordic Institute for Advanced Training in Occupational Health (NIVA), The Nordic Expert Group for Criteria Documentation of Health Risks from Chemicals (NEG), European Technology Platform on Industrial Safety (ETPIS), European Technology Platform in Additive Manufacturing (AMPlatform), and the Society for Risk Analysis.

The objective is to communicate the projects outcomes to these associations and platforms and use them as a channel to reach their members who are interested in Safe by Design of nanomaterials and nano enabled products. Moreover, the project aims to contribute to the roadmaps, white papers, guidelines and public reports will help shape the future of the recommendation and implementation of SAbyNA Platform by the stakeholders

4.1.7 Coordination with other projects

The consortium of SAbyNA will establish and maintain strong communication links with other projects which are funded under the same topic and under the umbrella of Nanosafety Cluster. This includes in particular the following projects: ASINA, SABYDOMA and SbD4Nano, to establish a common dialogue to avoid duplication of work and find synergies Others that are under execution since a longer time will also be contacted through the Nanosafety Cluster. This collaboration will also help harmonizing data structures and ontologies (data management plan).

Furthermore, SAbyNA will reach out to pilot line projects through the European Pilot Plant Network project (EPPN). Leitat as a partner in EPPN will allow SAbyNA to reach Horizon 2020 pilot projects and pilot line owners to inform them about SAbyNA Guidance Platform and the possibility for them to implement it in the future.

4.1.8 Standardization bodies

The SAbyNA consortium will work closely with standardization bodies such as the OECD, ISO and CEN (participating in their committees or activities), the Advisory Board for Safety & Health Regulations (under the Finnish Ministry of Social Affairs and Health), the Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) of the European Chemical Agency (ECHA), the Environment Agency & Department of the Environment, and the Food and Rural Affairs (Defra) (UK). These engagement activities with standardisation and regulatory bodies have direct input to the test methodologies chosen. Moreover, the bodies will be informed regarding data generated within the project which may influence standards under development and regulatory recommendations on safety requirements to be included in new/ revised guidelines.

4.2 Communication activities

4.2.1 Branding

During the execution of the project, the objective of the branding is to keep it as it is, make sure the consortium partners use it correctly as presented above and disseminate it as largely as possible by including it in all channels and materials.

4.2.2 Project website

The website will be constantly maintained, monitored, and updated. It will be enriched with additional content, might it be static or dynamic. The static content includes the core of the project such as the objectives, state-of-the-art, and partly results. The dynamic part is about the news and publications sections. There, all project activities will be announced, might it be milestones, participation in events, meetings, or any other dissemination activity. The publications section will be a public repository of all dissemination materials such as posters, presentations, scientific articles, public deliverables and communication materials. This way, the visitor will have access to all public documents produced by the project consortium in one place.

In addition, the website will be updated according to the needs of the consortium and state of the project. It aims to be flexible and will be adapted to the content the partners want to promote.

Leitat will push partners to provide information about their activities but also pull information and publish it with their approval and revision.

4.2.3 Leaflet

The first version of the leaflet has been released at the beginning of the project, published online, printed and distributed to the partners of the consortium. It has been presented in this document in the above section. Now, the goal is to increase its distribution to a maximum number of stakeholders. This might be done digitally and physically. In the short run, due to travel and events restrictions, the digital channels will be used. As its content is of great quality, its distribution in pieces (i.e. page by page focusing on the infographics), will be a good way to do so. Social media such as LinkedIn and Twitter will be the main distribution channels.

New versions will be produced during the project execution depending on the needs of the consortium. The content will be updated. The objective is to create at least one after two years of execution and a final one.

4.2.4 Infographics

As said in the previous section about infographics, the already existing infographics will be disseminated as widely as possible, especially social media but will also be used on the project website and project presentations made by the consortium partners. New ones will be created according to the demand of the project partners. Leitat stays at their entire availability to help them in disseminating the project. The objective is to create at least 5 more infographics during the project execution.

4.2.5 Press release

According to the execution of the project and the progress made in the development of the Guidance Platform, more press releases will be written and published by Leitat with the support of the entire consortium. The objective is to publish at least two more, one when the first version of the Platform is released and a second one for the second version of the Platform. Each will be distributed to the media contacts of Leitat and other project partners.

4.2.6 Video

The project will produce a project video describing the SAbyNA Guidance Platform. It should be a pitch of less than two minutes presenting the main features and benefits of the Platform. It will be done either when the first or second version of the Platform is released. It aims to help in the presentation of the Platform and reach new audiences. The video will then be disseminated on all channels such as web and social media.

4.2.7 Newsletter

Each year, a newsletter will be published summing up the main activities and progress made by the project consortium. It will only contain public disclosable information. It will be sent to all project stakeholders such as the ones who subscribed through the website but also disseminated on the website and social media. The newsletters will be visually attractive including infographics, semi-technical content about each technical work package and main dissemination activities performed.

4.2.8 Social media

The main social media channel of the project will be its Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/SAbyNA2020>) that will interact with the main actors of the nanosafety and safe by design field at world level, although there will be a European focus. Content will be published daily event much of it will be content from other sources. The personal LinkedIn accounts of some researchers will be used to post content related to the project as many of them benefit from a great network. At the end of the project, a wide community and audience will be created that will be a great asset for the exploitation of the Guidance Platform.

5. Conclusion

The communication materials produced for SAbyNA are already and will be for the entire project of a great help for all the consortium members. It will help them to promote a common image and with high quality materials that will improve the quality of the message. For digital or physical communication as well as dissemination activities, these materials will be of a great help. The materials will be updated on a regular basis whenever it is considered necessary by the consortium to make sure that the content is aligned with the current state of the project and the strategy of the consortium.

The aim in the short run is to increase the digital presence, and in the long run also physical presence, of the project by the creation of social media accounts and website. All the SAbyNA consortium has worked together in establishing a common baseline and message to transmit through all our channels, that will be re-visited periodically as the project will be advancing. At the same time, several multimedia content such as a presentation video, dissemination supporting material (poster, leaflet...) will be created to enhance the future impact.

To sum up, Leitat as hereby elaborated a communication and dissemination strategy that should serve as the basis for a successful forthcoming dissemination and communication. A second communication and dissemination report planned for the end of the project (M48) will update this strategy. Thus, based on the present report, related activities will be assessed and improved for the sake of SAbyNA